

THE 'NĀGABANDHA' AND THE 'PAÑCĀNGAVĪRA' CEILING

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While writing "The ceiling of the Temples in Gujarāt"¹, J. M. Nanavāṭī and I had to forego detailed discussion on two popular 'illustrative' types of ceilings met inside the halls of the fifteenth century Western Indian Jaina temples. That was because no helpful light then seemed coming from the mediaval manuals in Sanskrit on architecture, nor from other contemporaneous writings incidentally taking notice of such ceilings. The first type depicts Kṛṣṇa trampling or humbling the serpent Kāliya in the River Yamunā, the second shows a curious human figure possessing five bodies commonly sharing a head and a single pair of arms, one of the arms usually carrying a dagger in striking posture².

In the first case the illustration could be identified without difficulty on the basis of the wellknown narration of the Kṛṣṇa-ḥlā legends, but the authority of the *vastuśāstra*-s behind the selfsame depiction was still wanting. In the second no identification could be attempted since no parallels of motif could be traced and nothing seemed explaining the idea underlying the motif. As for the *kāliya-mardana* scene, a significant reference has of late been traced in the wellknown Western Indian *vastu* work, the *Aparājita-ṅr̥ccha* of Bhūvanādēva³ (ca. 3rd quarter of the 12th century) and has been discussed by me elsewhere⁴. The present paper is intended to focus more on the second motif and to identify if not quite explain it on the basis of the literary evidence which I of late could trace.

The fifteenth century temples which illustrate one or both of these two types of ceilings are : one of the five Jaina temples at Jesalmere⁵ and the Dhārāṇa vibhāra at Rāṇākpur (1440 and later),⁶ both in Rājasthāna, and the so called Melak-vasāhi (anc. Khārātara-vasāhi) atop Mt. Gīrnār (1455) in Saurāṣṭrā.⁷ And one more instance, which is anterior to these all since datable to around 1320, is the beautiful though misnamed Bhulavaṇī temple, also known as Vimāla-vasī (anc. Kharātara-vasāhi) on Mt. Śatruṅjaya,⁸ again in Saurāṣṭrā, illustrated and discussed here.

The identification of these two illustrative types becomes possible on account of some pilgrims' psalms written in the fifteenth century *a propos* of Śatruṅjaya and Gīrnār temples mentioned in the foregoing para. Referring briefly to the plan and interior arrangement of the 'Kharātara-vasāhi' on Śatruṅjaya hills, the unknown author of the *Śatruṅjaya caityaparipatī*⁹ thus mentions : 'There is, inside, (the ceiling depicting) *nāgabandha*, and again (the one showing) the alluring *pañcāṅga vīra*.'

Taham nāgaha bandha pūṇa bhūṣaṇa vira-pañcāṅga moha-i; 13,

The contemporaneous author Depala, a merited poet of his times, specially wrote a short but charming song in old Gujarāṭi on Śatruñjaya's selfsame Kharatara-vasahi, wherein he too takes note of the two aforementioned ceilings.⁴⁰ The poet remarks : '[And indeed] one forgets hunger and thirst while lost in-intently watching the pañcāṅga-vira and the nāgabandha (ceilings)':

bhukha ana-i trisa visara-i-e Pañcāṅga-vira nāgabandha nihālatān. 7

Turning now to the kharatara-vasahi at Ġirnār, we encounter a specific reference made in [a hitberto unpublished]⁴¹ *Ġirnār-caitya-paripāṭi* of the nāgabandha and the pañcāṅga-vira (ceilings) along with pūṭali-s (icons of apsaras-nāyikā-s in the raṅgamaṇḍapa (theatrical hall) of the selfsame temple :

Raṅgamaṇḍapi nāgabandha nihāla-u pūṭali-ē maṇḍapi mana vāla-u
Pañcāṅga-vira vasekhi-i-e māḷā-khāda-i maṇḍapa jānu. 29

As for the nāgabandha (snake-tangle) ceiling, it is obviously derived from the earlier Kāliya-damana type. In instances of the latter type, the nāga-s and the nāginī-s are shown in half human form, generally three on either side of the central figure of Kṛṣṇa trampling Kāliya. But in the nāgabandha type, the human-figural representation of the praying nāga-s and nāginī-s is subdued and reduced in significance, and it is the 'coils' which receive prominence, forming in many and multiple folds, a mesh or a complex tangle : (cf. figs. 1 & 3). I, at this point, reproduce the exquisite ceiling in the mukhacātuṣkī (entrance-porch) of the maṇḍapa (hall) of the Śiva temple at Mūla-Mādhavapura (ca. early 11th century) for comparison (fig. 5), and this would demonstrate how inside of two to three centuries the changes took place in the details, even when the conception remained unchanged.

As for the significance of the Pañcāṅga-vira ceiling, what its symbolism could be, is hard to guess. Vira is of course a 'warrior' or a 'hero of the battle field.' The dagger in the hand so signifies, just as it explains the motive. But what about the 'five bodies' ? Does it mean a hero possessing or revealing in battle the strength or prowess equivalent of five men ? Or is he one of the Fifty-two Vira-spirits of the folk tales ? Some explanation of this may be there in ancient literature, but until it is found, it must remain both curious and mysterious !

Notes and References :

1. Cf. author's long paper (written conjointly with J. M. Nanavati) covering the entire issue of the *Bulletin of Museum and Picture Gallery*, Baroda, namely vols. XVI-XVII, Baroda 1963.

Pañcāṅga-vīra ceiling, Kharatara-vasahi,
S'atruñjaya, ca. 1320 A. D. (Copyright
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Pañcāṅga-vīra ceiling Dharāṇa-vihāra, Rāṅaka-
pura, 1440 A. D. (Copyright M. A. Dhaky)

Nāgabandha ceiling Kharatara-vasahi,
S'atruṅjaya, ca. 1320 A. D. (Copyright
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Pañcāngavīra ceiling, Dharaṇa-vihāra, Rāṇaka-
pura, 1440 A. D. (Copyright M. A. Dhaky).

Nāgadamana or Kāliya-mardana ceiling mukhacatuṣkī S'iva temple, Mūla-Mādhavpur, ca. early 11th century. (Copyright and courtesy, Archaeological Research Society, Porbandar).

Alāu Pārśvanātha temple, Nāgadā, Mewar, Rajasthan, ca. 2nd quarter of the 11th century. (By courtesy and assistance, The American Institute of Indian Studies, Varanasi).

2. We then classed it under "Kautukī (curious) figures":
3. Ed. Popaṭbhai Ambashankar Mankad, *Gaekwad's Oriental Series*, No. CXV, Baroda, 1950, chap. 218/36
4. Cf. 'Nāgadamana-ni Chata ane Vastuśāstra-vidhāna' (Guj.), *Purātana*, Porbandara 1973. pp. 122-123 & fig. *contra* p. 38,
5. Cf. H. Bhisham Pal, *The Temples of Rajasthan*, Alwar-Jaipur 1969, fig. 91. The author does not say in which temple at Jesalmere does it occur. One of my older notes, which however is unsupported by source-reference, mentions this type of ceiling in the Lakṣmaṇa Vihāra there. Whether this is the same, or otherwise, I am unable to decide since never visited Jesalmere.
6. Pt. Ambalal Premchand Shah, *Rāṇakpur-ni Pañcatīrthi* (Guj) First Ed., Bhāvnagar V. S. 2012 (A. D. 1956), fig. 23; here see figs. 3&4. These are located in the central bay of the lowermost storey of the two storied (Western) *balāṇaka* (entry-hall), and the forebay of the second storey of the selfsame *balāṇaka*. There is one more ceiling of the *nāgabandha* type in this temple, in the Southern Mēghanāda hall, in the upper storey there.
7. See Sarabhai Nawab, *Jaina Tīrthas in India and Their Architecture*, Ahmedabad 1944 fig. 195.
8. I am discussing that temple at some length (in collaboration with Shri Amritlal Trivedi) in *Śatruñjaya Mahātīrtha-nāṇi Jaina-mandiro* (Guj.), now in the final stage.
9. Ed. Shriyut Sarabhai Manilal Nawab, 'Pandarmā Saikā-ni Śatruñjaya Caitya-Pari-pāṭi' (Guj.) *Śri Jaina Satya Prakāśa*, Year 12, No. 3, Sr. No. 135, dt. 15-12-46, pp. 96-97.
10. I am at present editing this in a special compilation of hitherto unknown psalms.
11. Smt. Vidhatriben Vora and myself are editing this psalm at present.

APPENDIX

The *Girnār-caitya-paripāṭi*, as mentioned earlier, takes notice of the *nāgabandha* ceilings in the Kharatara-vasahi, on the Girnār hills. But the ceiling there surely does not betray the *nāgabandha* motif: Instead, one meets Viṣṇu encircled by human figures, whether the *gōpa*-s (young cowherds or demons being vanquished by Him, it is hard to decide: (Cf. Nawab fig. 197). A third ceiling in the Kharatara-vasahi on Śatruñjaya also depicts the same theme. One more instance is a huge stele found from near the older temple of Mādhavarāya at Mādhavapura in Saurāṣṭra and now transferred to the Junagadh Museum. The purport of this theme is still unclear, but it surely is not the *nāgabandha*, and the writer of the *Girnār-caitya-paripāṭi* mistook the motif it seems.

Sambodhi 4.3-4

LIST OF ILLUSTRATIONS

1. *Pañcāṅga-vira* ceiling, Kharatara-vasahi, Satruñjaya, ca. 1320 A. D.
(Copyright L. D. Institute of Indology, Ahmedabad)
2. *Pañcāṅga-vira* ceiling, Dharāṇa-vihāra, Rāṇakpur, 1440 A. D.
(Copyright M. A. Dhaky.)
3. *Nagabandha* ceiling, Kharatara-vasahi, Satruñjaya, ca. 1323 A. D.
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4. *Pañcāṅga-vira* ceiling, Dharāṇa vihāra, Rāṇakpur, 1440. A. D.
(Copyright M. A. Dhaky)
5. *Nagadamāna* or *Kāliya-mardāna* ceiling, mukhacatuṣṭi, Śiva temple, mūla-Mādhavapura, ca. early 11th century. (Copyright and courtesy Archaeological Research Society, Porbandar.)

APPENDIX

The Girnar-cave-paints, as mentioned earlier, takes notice of the *nāgavandha* ceiling in the Kharatara-vasahi on the Girnar hills. But the ceiling there surely does not betray the *nāgavandha* motif; instead, one meets *Yama* enclosed by four figures, whether the *gopas* (young cowherds) or *ganas* being vanquished by Him, it is hard to decide: (C. Nawab fig. 197). A third ceiling in the Kharatara-vasahi on Satruñjaya also depicts the same theme. One more instance is a huge stele found near the older temple of Mādhavapura at Mādhavapura in Saurashtra and now transferred to the Junagadh Museum. The purport of this theme is still unclear, but it surely is not the *nāgavandha*, and the writer of the Girnar-cave-paints mistake the motif it seems.